

EPIDEMIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF BREAST CANCER IN THE FERGANA REGION

Parpiyeva Odinaxon Rakhmanovna

Associate Professor Central Asian Medical University.

e.mail: parpieva.odinahon@yandex.ru, ORCID: 0000-0001-6223-103X
Fergana, Uzbekistan.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17348802>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 11th October 2025

Accepted: 13th October 2025

Online: 14th October 2025

KEYWORDS

breast cancer, incidence rate, mortality rate, survival.

ABSTRACT

Today, our medicine has made significant advances in the fight against breast cancer. Despite this, it remains the most common disease among women worldwide. Each year, 665,000 women worldwide die from breast cancer. The survival rate for breast cancer is 55%. Without adequate treatment, this figure drops to 10%. Many factors influence survival rates. If survival is determined by tumor stage, then in the early stages, it ranges from 95-100%. However, timely diagnosis and treatment, combined surgery and chemotherapy, strict adherence to doctor's recommendations, a healthy lifestyle, and a balanced diet can help overcome this disease to a certain extent

Introduction. Breast cancer is the most common form of cancer in women and is the leading cause of death from this type of disease in Uzbekistan. Breast cancer diagnosed at an early stage has a favorable prognosis and high survival rates. The survival rate for stages 1 and 2 of cancer is almost 100 percent. Therefore, it is important to develop and test a National, integrated program for breast cancer control, which includes measures to inform patients, refer them to screening and treatment, as well as create a screening and cancer registry. As a result, the proposed program will help detect breast cancer in women early - at stages I-II. In turn, this will allow for surgical treatment of cancer, increasing the chances of survival.

Objective: To conduct an epidemiological analysis of breast cancer incidence rates in the Fergana region in 2020-2024, that is, the last 5 years.

Material and methods. Within the framework of this research, the dynamics of morbidity and mortality rates of patients diagnosed with breast cancer were studied and analyzed based on statistical data from the Fergana regional branch of RIO and RIATM for 2020-2024. The research used Microsoft Excel.

Results. In 2024, 530 cases of breast cancer were detected in Fergana region. During 2020-2024, 2,255 cases of breast cancer were detected in Fergana region. Compared to 2020-2023, an increase in this indicator was observed in 2024 (in 2020 - 356, in 2021 - 414, in 2022 - 454, in 2023 - 501).

When analyzing the dynamics of the distribution of breast cancer, in 2020 - 77.6%, in 2021 - 72.2%, in 2022 - 77.8%, in 2023 - 74.8%, in 2024 - 73.8% of patients the disease was detected in stages I-II. The share of patients with breast cancer in stages III-IV was 22.4% in

2020, 27.8% in 2021, 22.2% in 2022, 25.2% in 2023, and 26.3% in 2024. The share of patients with breast cancer in stages III-IV remains high.

According to the generalized data on epidemiological indicators, in Fergana region, 2426 oncological diseases were detected for the first time in 2020, of which 356 (14.7%) were breast cancer, 2616 oncological diseases were detected for the first time in 2021, of which 414 (15.8%) were breast cancer, 2694 oncological diseases were detected for the first time in 2022, of which 454 (16.8%) were breast cancer, 2723 oncological diseases were detected for the first time in 2023, of which 501 (18.4%) were breast cancer, 2843 oncological diseases were detected for the first time in 2024, of which 530 (18.6%) were breast cancer.

In 2024, the highest incidence rate was 22.8% in Furkat district, 21.7% in Kuvasoy city, and 17.4% in Fergana city. The lowest incidence rate was observed in Buvayda district (8.5%), Bogdod district (9.0%) and Qoshtepa district (9.1%). The highest mortality rate was 9.5% in Fergana district, 7.5% in Fergana city, and 6.9% in Kuvasoy city. The lowest mortality rate was observed in Sokh district - 1.2%.

Based on the above, it can be seen that the mortality rate is increasing year by year.

Conclusion. When analyzing the incidence of breast cancer among the population of Fergana region from 2020 to 2024, a year-on-year increase in the rate of newly diagnosed breast cancer is observed in the region. This is explained by the low level of planned oncological care in terms of early detection of this pathology among women. However, despite the improvement in 5-year survival rates for patients with breast cancer in Fergana region, the overall incidence rate and one-year mortality rate are steadily increasing.

References:

1. Yazıcı, O., Özdemir, N. (2018). Meme Kansyerinde Epidemiyolojik Vyerilyer, Risk Faktörlyeri, Risk Azaltıcı Yaklaşımlar. Türkiye Klinikleri Tıbbi Onkoloji-Özel Konular, 11(1), 1-7.
2. Pisegna, J.; Xu, M.; Spees, C.; Krok-Schoen, J.L. Mental health-related quality of life is associated with diet quality among survivors of breast cancer. *Support. Care Cancer* 2021, 29, 2021-2028.
3. Brown, J.C.; Sarwyer, D.B.; Troxel, A.B.; Sturgeon, K.; DeMichele, A.M.; Denlinger, C.S.; Schmitz, K.H. A randomized trial of exercise and diet on health-related quality of life in survivors of breast cancer with overweight or obesity. *Cancer* 2021, 127, 3856-3864.
4. Parpiyeva O.R. -ASSESSMENT OF THE MAIN INDICATORS OF BREAST CANCER IN THE TERRITORIES OF THE FERGANA REGION//New Day in Medicine 4(78)2025 1121-1126 https://newdayworldmedicine.com/en/new_day_medicine/4-78-2025.
5. Normatova, S. A., & Parpiyeva, O. R. (2024). Assessment of the role of risk factors in the development of breast cancer. *Theory and Analytical aspects of recent research*, 2(21), 74- 78.
6. Parpiyeva, O. (2023). Ko'krak bezi saratoni bilan kasallangan ayollar ovqatlanishini korrektsiyalashni ilmiy asoslash (adabiyotlar tahlili). *Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук*, 3(12), 168-177.
7. Rakhmanovna, P. O. (2022). Nutrition and diet in breast cancer. *Texas Journal of Medical Science*, 7, 27-30.

8. Parpieva, O. R., Muydinova, E., & Safarova, G. (2021). Breast cancer. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(11), 482-485.
10. Парпиева, О. Р., Эрматова, Г. А., Камалова, Д. А., & Якубов, А. (2024). КОРРЕЛЯЦИОННАЯ СВЯЗЬ МЕЖДУ ПИТАНИЕМ И СОСТОЯНИЕМ ЗДОРОВЬЯ ЖЕНЩИН РЕПРОДУКТИВНОГО ВОЗРАСТА. *JOURNAL OF MEDICINE AND PHARMACY*, 7(6), 4-10.
11. Парпиева, О. Р. (2023). КЎКРАК БЕЗИ САРАТОНИ ҲАҚИДА ТУШУНЧА. *Finland International Scientific Journal of Education. Social Science & Humanities*, 11(3), 446-454.
12. Парпиева О. (2024). ЭПИДЕМИОЛОГИЧЕСКОЕ РАСПРОСТРАНЕНИЕ РАКА МОЛОЧНОЙ ЖЕЛЕЗЫ НА ТЕРРИТОРИЯХ ФЕРГАНСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ. *Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук*, 4(10), 281–288.
13. Parpiyeva Odinaxon Rahmanovna - Central Asian Medical University. (2025). FARG'ONA VILOYATI HUDUDLARI KESIMIDA KO'KRAK BEZI SARATONI BILAN KASALLANISHNING STATISTIK TAHLILI. В *ActaCAMU* (Т. 11, Выпуск 1, сс. 157–164). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17181703>.
14. Normatova Sh.A., Parpiyeva O.R. (2024). KO'KRAK BEZI SARATONI BILAN OG'RIGAN BEMORLAR OVQATLANISH HOLATINI O'RGANISH NATIJALARI. *Actacamu*, 7(7), 30–33. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14131853>.
15. Parpiyeva, O. (2024). KO'KRAK BEZI SARATONINING FARG'ONA VILOYATI HUDUDLARI KESIMIDA EPIDEMIOLOGIK TARQALISHI. В *EURASIAN JOURNAL OF MEDICAL AND NATURAL SCIENCES* (Т. 4, Выпуск 10, сс. 281–288). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14038694>.